

ABOUT ALISHER NAVOI'S USE OF THE IMAGE OF THE HEART

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Poetry is a translator of heart and soul. It discusses the whole being, man and the universe, truth and justice. The most delicate feelings are depicted in unique colors and tones. Unfathomable mysteries and beauties are discovered by the power of thought. All this is solved by means of an artistic word or a poetic image, which embodies power and magic.

If you look at the science of literary studies, you can observe that image and symbol are often considered or evaluated as the same thing. There is a reason for this, of course, because the image contains all the characteristics of the symbol, and at the same time, the symbol also reflects a certain edge of the image. However, image and symbol cannot be used in the same sense. The image is the main tool of artistic thinking, an important form of expressing ideological content. A symbol is a picture, a pattern, a picture; symbol, example, symbol; form, parable, example; it is explained as "some example given from a different thing, incident, incident for explanation or as a basis, evidence, proof". In another sense, it is noted that it is an image, a figure, a vision embodied in the eyes, in the mind, in the imagination (It is the next explanation that caused the symbol to be used for the same purpose as the image). In our opinion, an image represents a broader meaning than a symbol. The emotional-emotional power, symbolic-figurative character is very deep in the image. The most important feature and decisive

importance of the poetic image is its reflection of emotional sincerity, color and tone, and spiritual essence in the poem. The poetic image opens a wide way to the inner world of a person through the inner features of the poem. Poetry is alive with image. Impressive with the image. That's why in a poem devoid of poetic image, mental-emotional privilege is completely limited, and the thought does not go beyond a dry statement. A symbol is not as complicated as an image. In most cases, it arises on the basis of artistic conditionality as a figurative and symbolic feature of the image. A symbol cannot always fully reflect the poet's ideological and artistic intention. Accordingly, a symbol can be said to be smaller than an image, a certain form of expression of an image.

As all lyrical genres have their own images, the ghazal also has a traditional system of images. The soul, which is a mirror of the human inner world, also belongs to this system of images. In literature, especially in poetry, the soul, which is the main word, is often the same image as the poet's "I". Other than the heart, no image or artistic tool can reflect the poet's feelings and experiences so deeply and vividly. This situation is also observed in Alisher Navoi's work.

Reacting to the fact that some literary experts compare Navoi's lyrics to a "calm flowing river" and Fuzuli's lyrics to a "quickly flowing stream", Navoi scholar A. Hayitmetov says: "In our opinion, to give such an assessment to Navoi's lyrics is to underestimate the emotional power of the poet's lyrics and to belittle it. is a thing. The very images of Navoi, which are connected to the eye or the heart, their great emotion, emotion, playfulness, unexpected new similes and comparisons, refute this idea. In such places, Navoi rises to the highest peak of the image of the movement of the soul."

In fact, Navoi achieved extremely high results in describing the experiences of the heart and heartache. The poet expressed his deep philosophical observations and thoughts about the world and man through mental images. In Navoi's lyrics, the soul comes in the form of a perfect person, a scholar, a leader, a sage, a thinker,

a lover, a friend, a friend. It is the soul that expresses the mental state of the hero and the highest level of the poet in the ghazal.

In Navoi's ghazals, the main focus of the poet is not to describe the beauty of the land, but to describe the pains and longings of the lover, his inner world. In such places, the poet discusses the secrets of the heart and love, describes the state of the heart through artistic images and symbolic images. Navoi interprets the heart as a treasure of divine secrets, the main basis of humanity with traditional symbolic and metaphorical symbols such as "boda", "may", "ko'zgu", "mehrob", "baytul ahzon", "butxona", "vayrona":

Эй харобот аҳли, соқий орази акси учун

Соф қилмоғлиғ била май кўзгусин сайқал қилинғ.

In the verse, «xarobot ahli», «soqiy», «may ko'zgusi» are symbolic figures. In order to understand the idea put forward by the poet, it is necessary to pay attention to the essence of these symbols. The people of Harobot are the people of enlightenment in the mystical sense and the perfect ones who have appeared in the knowledge. Saqi is the Truth, whose grace is absolute, the basis of all grace and love. May's mirror is the heart. So, as expressed in the verse, only if the "mirror of May" - the heart is pure, then "the beauty of truth" - the beauty of the Truth will shine. With the thought in this verse, Navoi emphasized the acquisition of divine breadth of the soul through purity, the fundamental basis of perfection. The poet expresses the same idea in another stanza as follows.

Бўл сафо аҳлига ҳамдам ёр васлин истасанг,

Аксини солгайму соқий бўлмагунча бода соф?

The people of “safo ahli” - people of the heart. Yor - Yor is the only God. A person who wants Allah's will should follow the leaders and the best people. The second verse can be interpreted both externally and internally. In other words, if the water is not clear, would it be reflected in the water? Or if the heart is not pure, would the truth be revealed?

In a poetic image, the main content of the poet is hidden or kept secret. Because "the poetic image belongs to the restless spirit and painful heart of the poet, rather than the poet's thoughts," writes literary critic I. Haqqul. "Poetic image is not a simple copy of real thing, event, person, etc. It is a re-perceived and enriched copy of a thing, an event, a person's creative feeling, imagination, and ideological intention." Therefore, its correct interpretation allows to understand the main meaning of the poem. The word "but" in the verse literally means a date worshiped by fire worshipers. Symbolically, it is a lover, friend, lover, symbol of Truth. A lover considers it infidelity to pray facing the Qibla, as long as the beauty of the Truth does not shine in his mihrab (heart). Its original purpose is to "ul kozgu" - to purify the heart "without a pattern". This is the need of true love.

In general, the talent of any poet is evaluated based on how and in which ways he expresses the truths of life and human feelings. The artist's attitude to words and images determines not only the form, but also the essence - the poet's worldview, the standard of imagination. Navoi follows the traditional way of reflecting the soul through symbolic and metaphorical images.